

CASE STUDIES OF EARTHEN DAM FAILURES DUE TO EARTHQUAKE AT BHUJ

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ABSTRACT

A disastrous earthquake of magnitude (ML)6.9 struck Bhuj and adjoining areas of Kachchh district in Gujarat in the morning of January, 26, 2001 which took a toll of human lives exceeding 18000 and caused extensive damage to over 6 lakh houses. The damage was maximum in Bhachau, Bhuj, Anjar, Gandhidham and Rapar talukas of Gujarat and in faraway places like Ahmedabad.

Besides loss of human lives and damages to civil engineering structures, this shallow focus seismic activity has also caused damages to several medium and minor irrigation schemes in Kachchh and in parts of Saurashtra region. Most of the dams were earthen dams.

The paper attempts to discuss the effect of earthquake on few such dams. It includes the study of how the different dams were damaged based on the distance from the epicentre and what mechanism was adopted to restore the earthen dams. Amongst the most affected dams were Rudramata, Kaswati, Kaila and Fatehgadh which are domestic water storage as well as irrigation schemes.

The study is part of the research project which was given to the author by International Commission on Irrigation and Drainage (ICID-CIID) immediately after the earthquake to assess the effect of earthquake on earthen dams and the impact of the damages to the drinking water supply of the region.

Keywords: earthen dams, failure of dams, restoration of dams

STUDY AREA

Kutch is an ancient land possessed of great antiquity, which takes its name from its geographical characteristics and topographical features resembling a tortoise. This crescent shaped region forms part of the northwest Gujarat. The district stretches roughly from 22°44'11" (approx.) to 24°41'25" (approx.) north latitudes and 68°09'46" (approx.) and 71°54'47" (approx.) east longitudes. There are 20 medium irrigation schemes located in Kutch district. (Gujarat tourism.com)

Bhuj is the administrative capital of Kutch district. It is geographically located roughly at the centre of the taluka. It has an average elevation of 110 metres. On the eastern side of the city is a hill known as that separates Bhuj city and town. There are four dams in the vicinity of Bhuj namely Rudramata, Kaswati, Fatehgadh and Kaila which are domestic water storage as well as irrigation schemes.

ABOUT THE BHUJ EARTHQUAKE

A disastrous earthquake of a magnitude (ML) 6.9 struck Bhuj and adjoining areas of Kutch district of Gujarat in the wee hours on 26th January, 2001. It's severity was so high that thousands of people were killed and several thousand injured. It also caused extensive damage to civil engineering structures including the earthen dams located in Kutch.

DAMAGES TO EARTHEN DAMS IN VICINITY OF BHUJ

There are 20 medium and 165 minor irrigation schemes in Kutch district. These are embankment dams (some of minor schemes are more than 15 m high) with chute spillway or Ground Bar Waste Weir. The reservoirs of majority of these earthfill dams were below the sill level, i.e. below minimum draw down level and few were almost empty due to the successive drought conditions. A large number of them had suffered severe to moderate damages. The details of the dams are given as follows:

Table 1 Heavily Damaged Medium Irrigation Schemes in Kutch District

Sr.no	Name of Scheme	Max. height in m	Length in m	Gross storage Mm3	Completion year	Approx. distance km	Direction from epicentre
1	Kasawati	8.81	1455	8.20	1976	38	WSW
2	Fatehgadh	11.28	4130	7.95	1987	67	ENE
3	Rudramata	27.58	1217	61.53	1959	57	WSW
4	Kalia	23.47	1066	8.95	1955	69	WSW

Fatehgadh Irrigation Scheme

The damages to the earth dam, spillway portion and head regulator were as follows:

Earth Dam Portion

- Longitudinal and transverse cracks at intervals on crest of dam starting from chainage 650m onwards.
- Extensive and large scale settlement in the top and upstream slope of the dam in the reach 3350 to 3700m.
- Settlement in the upstream and downstream slope pitching at many places.
- Very deep rain cuts on d/s slope of dam aggravated further by climbing of animals like buffaloes etc.
- Settlement around right side key-wall of wing wall of spillway.

Spillway Portion

- Cracks in left wing wall of spillway in the downstream reach.
- Parapet wall over both wing walls of spillway damaged.

Intake well / Head regulator

- Surface cracks in the stone masonry structure of the left side.
- Super-structure of right side head regulator damaged.

Kaila Irrigation Scheme

The damages to the earth dam, spillway portion and head regulator are as follows:

Earth dam portion

- Fissures are noticed at many places along the upstream slope of the earth dam.
- Settlement of pitching and earthwork has taken place at many places on the u/s slope.
- Longitudinal cracks have been noticed on the top of the dam in 50m length.
- Transverse cracks have been found at many places along the body of the dam.
- Slippage of earthwork is noticed on the downstream slope of the earth dam.
- Settlement of the top of the dam has taken place at some places.
- Cracks have been noticed on the d/s slope of the dam along with settlement of the earthwork and the pitching.

Spillway Portion

- Certain cracks are noticed in the body of the walls of the spillway.
- Cracks are also noticed in the wing walls on u/s as well as on the d/s .
- End sill is also damaged at certain locations.
- Construction joints in the downstream wall have opened out.

Intake Well / Head regulator

- The super structure of the intake well cabin has been badly damaged.
- Wide cracks are noticed in the cabin of the head regulator.
- Foot bridge piers have been crushed and seperated.

Kaswati Irrigation Scheme

The damages to the earth dam, spillway portion and head regulator were as follows:

Earth Dam Portion

- Longitudinal cracks and transverse cracks in the crest of the dam were found for almost the entire length of the dam in different patches.
- Major deep crack running longitudinally along the centre of the crest in the chainage 650 to 920m with depth of the crack more than 5m was noticed.

- Differential settlement of the upstream portion of the fill of the dam was noticed.
- Sliding of the slopes has taken place near the top of the dam around chainage 740m and near the lower level around 880m.
- Longitudinal cracks were noticed near the upper portion of the downstream slope running parallel to the central longitudinal crack were noticed in some reaches.
- Settlement of upstream pitching in different patches along the length of the dam.

Spillway Portion

- No significant damages to the spillway portion of the dam was noticed.

Intake well / head Regulator

- Diagonal crack noticed around circumference of the circular intake well.
- Reinforcement of longitudinal beams of approach structure exposed at some places with minor cracks at the bottom of beam.
- Crack in wing walls of approach channel to intake gate.
- Cracks in columns of superstructure near the top.

Rudramata Irrigation Scheme

The damages to the earth dam, spillway portion and head regulator were as follows:

Earth Dam Portion

- Longitudinal and transverse cracks at dam top near the head regulator.
- Longitudinal cracks (2 to 3) running parallel near downstream crest/ slope region.
- Transverse cracks noticed at the top of the dam.
- Settlement in patches in pitching of the upstream slope from 90 to 400 m chainage with severely affected portion between 250 to 410m. Very deep cracks with depth more than 3 m and width more than 5” to 6” were seen in the portion just above the MDDL.
- Settlement in downstream slope of the earth dam with prominent settlement in portion between chainage 410 to 435m.
- Seepage observed downstream of the d/s toe around chainage 350m after the occurrence of the earthquake.

Spillway Portion

- There was no significant damage to the Ogee spillway and the stilling basin area.
- The top portion of the left abutment wall adjoining the stairs had collapsed.

Intake Well / Head Regulator

- Parapet walls of the approach bridge had collapsed in the initial reach.
- Super structure of the intake well had developed severe cracks in the columns.
- Cracks had developed in the approach channel walls running diagonally around 15m from the emergency gate.

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DAMAGES

The damage to the earthen dams due to the earthquake was noticed in various types. Looking to the types of damages, various parameters attributing to the damage were mainly classified as:

1. The type of soil strata – i.e the geological formations.
2. The type of dam section.
3. Orientation of the dam.
4. Age of the dam.
5. Level of water in reservoir at the time of earthquake.
6. Connectivity between various body materials of the dam.
7. Zone of the isosiesmal in which the dam lies and the distance from the epicentre.

The influence of the above factors has been discussed in detail as follows.

Type of the soil strata – i.e geological formations

The type of soil strata and the type of the bed rock in the foundation of the dam have played a major role in the extent of damages to the dams. It has been observed that the dams located in the areas where there was a major part of sandstone e.g Kaswati, Fatehgadh had damage to a greater extent as compared to those situated in other types of foundation rocks. Table 2 shows shows the type of the bed rock on which the dams have been constructed.

Table 2 Type of Bedrock and Extent of damages

Sr.No.	Name of Dam	Type of Bedrock
1	Fatehgadh	Sandstone + Limestone
2	Kaila	Sandstone + Limestone
3	Kasvati	Sandstone
4	Rudramata	Sandstone

Type of Dam Section

In the Kutch region, mainly sandy clay or medium black soil with fine sand is found. This type of soil has less cohesive power, high permeability and less plasticity. Therefore, homogeneous sections of earthen dams are not possible in this region. So all earthen dams in the Kutch region have been constructed as non-homogeneous type dams. As the impervious hearting material is not available nearby the site, the cost of transporting the hearting material is very high. So in many of the dams, the slope provided in the hearting material is inadequate as economy in cost of construction could have been a reason.

Orientation of the body of Dam

The orientation of the body of dam in the layout has played a key role in the type of damage to the body of the dam. The portions of the dams which are parallel to the east-west direction have longitudinal cracks along the top as well as on the slopes of the dams. The part of the body of the dam which is perpendicular to the east-west direction has transverse cracks in the body of the dam. If the extent of the transverse cracks is very large, seepage has been large.

Age of the dam

Some of the dams of the medium irrigation schemes of Kutch were constructed about 40-50 years ago when the technology was not so advanced. In case of earth dams, actually age acts as a beneficial factor but in this case it has played adversely as most of the dams have been built with the locally available soil which has very little cohesive power. Also, they may not have been compacted properly at the time of construction. The hearting material used in these dams is also of inferior quality resulting in cracks in the body of dam.

Table 3 Age of the dams of medium irrigation schemes

Sr No	Name of Scheme	Age in years	Damages
1	Fatehgadh	22	Major
2	Kaila	49	Major
3	Kasvati	28	Major
4	Rudramata	42	Major

Level of water in the reservoir

Monsoon is observed mainly in the months of June, July and August in Kutch region. In this region, the height of dams is less as compared to the other regions. Depth of water in the reservoir is also less. So the water in the reservoirs is mainly observed upto the month of March. The earthquake had occurred in the month of January. Due to the successive drought condition, the water level in most of the dams was below the minimum drawdown level and was almost less in some of the dams. But those dams which were to cater to the water supply demand in the coming summer, some water level was observed and therefore their soil was in a saturated condition. This saturated condition of soil has also played a role in the damage of the dams.

As a result, dams having water in the reservoir portion have developed slope failures or settlement on the upstream faces. Settlement of pitching has also been observed on the upstream slope in such cases. E.g Rudramata, Kasvati

Connectivity between various body materials of the dam.

It has been observed that dams which have a combination of corewall and hearting material with the casing material have been damaged to a greater extent. This may have occurred due to the uneven settlement of the different types of the materials and the non-uniform transfer of the shocks of earthquake to the body of the dam. e.g. Kaila have more damages as compared to those having no core wall but flatter slope of hearting.

Distance from epicentre

It has been observed that dams closer to the epicentre have more damages as compared to those situated at a greater distance from the epicentre. E.g. Rudramata, Kaswati, Kaila. On an average, the variation of extent of damages from major to medium is observed in a radius of 90 km from the epicentre.

The intensity of the damages reduces with the change in the isoseismals zones, i.e the damages to the dams situated in the isoseismal zone X is maximum, to those situated in isoseismal zone IX ranges from major to medium and to those situated in isoseismal zone VIII is of minor scale.

Table 4 Distance of the dams from the epicentre.

Sr No	Name of Scheme	Distance from Epicentre in km	Damages
1	Fatehgadh	110	Major
2	Kaila	33	Major
3	Kasvati	28	Major
4	Rudramata	28	Major

OBSERVATIONS & CONCLUSIONS

A team of experts in various fields have accompanied me during my three phase visit to the earthen dams in Kutch region after earthquake and during the restoration and repair work.

We had discussed with the local engineers in charge of the medium irrigation schemes, Director of Gujarat Engineering Research Institute, Managing Director of Gujarat Water Resources Development Corporation etc.

The following conclusions were drawn as a result of our observations, analysis and discussions.

*Orientation

Main damages to the structures are observed in the east-west direction. The dams in east-west direction have longitudinal cracks about 5-15 cm wide, 1-3 m deep and 10-100 m long cracks. E.g. Rudramata, Kaswati, Fatehgadh.

The portion of the dams in the north-south direction has transverse cracks in the body of the dam. E.g. Fatehgadh and Kaswati.

*Geology

The geology of the area has played a major role in the extent of the damages to the dams – dams located in the sandy strata have been damaged to a greater extent.

Majorities of the dams lie on sandy strata. So the casing material is containing high sand. Hearting material has to be transported from a long distance. So nearby soil containing fine sand is used as a hearting material. The soils containing sands have less plasticity and cohesion. So dams on sandy strata show major damage. E.g. Don, Rudramata, Kaswati, Kaila.

*Development of Cracks

Mainly cracks are observed at the junctions of casing and hearting material or hearting material and diaphragm. As a result of cumulative action of a series of shocks, vibrations have had different types of effects on different types of soils. Soils containing sand have settled more as compared to soils containing more clay. So due to uneven settlement of soil, cracks are found in the body of the dams.

*Level of water in the reservoir.

The dams having higher water level in the reservoir have major failures on the upstream side of the dam. This is due to the settlement of the saturated soil. In such dams, upstream heel portion has settled.

*Distance from the epicentre

It has been noted that the dams nearer to the epicentre have incurred more damages. The entire Kutch region lies in the isoseismal zones X, XI and VIII from the epicentre. Those dams located in the isoseismal zone X i.e Rudramata, Kaswati, Kaila have been damaged the most

*Seepage

Seepage was noticed on the downstream side of the Rudramata dam. This was due to the transverse cracks in the body of the dam.

*Effect on related structures

Cracks have been found on the intake well, valve operation cabin on the head regulator of the canals, on pipe culverts of transportation system. Some of the structures have collapsed and some have developed severe cracks. Majority of these structures have been constructed in rubble masonry.

Photographs of Damages to Dams Visited

Cracks on top of dam in Fatehgadh dam	Upstream slope failure in Fatehgadh dam
Downstream slope failure in Fatehgadh dam	Settlement on upstream slope in Kaswati dam
Cracks on top of dam in Kaswati dam	Cracks on top of dam in Rudramata dam

<p>Settlement near upstream toe in Rudramata dam</p>	<p>Cracks on Kaswati dam</p>
<p>Cracks on top of Kaswati dam</p>	<p>Reservoir of Kaswati dam</p>

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